

Protection of User Data Privacy in Presidential Election Campaign: Learn From United States' Case

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Abstract

In this modern era, social networking has become very popular, with most people using the services of several social media platforms. With the increase in the use of social media, the issue of privacy of personal data has arisen. This paper will discuss the issue of private data protection in Indonesia ahead of the 2019 Presidential Election. It will also discuss the impact of the unauthorised use of personal data obtained from social media accounts, especially Facebook. This study employs the analytical and descriptive research methods. Data collection was done by literature research; library research was performed to obtain secondary data, and a literature review of some online media references, such as online magazine sites from several countries. We conclude that there is no legal umbrella protecting Indonesians with respect to the safety of their personal data. Therefore, the country may be vulnerable to cyber media-based campaigns as we move towards the 2019 Presidential Election.

Keywords: Social Media; Facebook; Data Privacy; Presidential Election

Introduction

In every social circle, almost everyone who uses smartphones has social media accounts, like Facebook, Twitter, Path, Pinterest, Instagram, etc. This situation has changed the way people communicate with each other in this modern era. In the past, people were more acquainted and relied on face-to-face interaction to get information.

Facebook, which is a social networking site launched in February 2004 in the United States, has become famous all over the world in recent years. According to official statistics, there are 845 million active Facebook users per month (Facebook, 2012). People can stay connected with friends, relatives, and close associates to share and reveal what is important to them and to discover what is going on in the world on Facebook (Winter K.W. Wong, 2012). Therefore, a person's privacy must be maintained on the site as it concerns the user's data.

Facebook has Terms and Conditions on user privacy, as written in the Facebook Privacy Principles:

Facebook is built to get people closer; we help you connect with friends and family, find local events, and find groups to join together. We realise that people use Facebook to compare, but everyone wants to share everything with everyone, including us. It's crucial that you have a choice when it comes to how your data is used. Here are principles that guide our approach to privacy on Facebook (Facebook, 2018).

Perhaps if we are careful in creating social media accounts, we must first read the terms and conditions of confidentiality, because we include personal data in the site, such as real name, address, age, occupation, religion, and others.

In Facebook Privacy Principle, there are points about Facebook keeping user's information; in this regard, personal data will be maintained. The end reads as follows:

We work hard to keep your information safe. We work around the clock to help protect people's accounts, and we build security on every Facebook product. Our security system runs millions of times every second to help capture threats automatically and delete them before they reach you. You can also use our security tools like two-factor authentication to help keep your account a lot safer (Facebook, 2018).

By this point, Facebook has a commitment to its users to keep personal accounts from unauthorised persons, and it must be done by managers of every social media site for the privacy and convenience of users.

Private data is data in the form of identity, codes, symbols, letters or numbers that are associated with a particular person (private). The term data protection was first used in Germany and Sweden in the 1970s, and it involves the protection of personal data through legislation. Obviously, in practice, there have been many violations committed by both government and private parties. However, personal data should not be misused, hence the necessary adjustments related to the problem of personal data (Latumahina, 2014).

In 2016, United States of America held a presidential election, with the major candidates, Hillary Clinton and Donald Trump, campaigning aggressively using various strategies to ensure victory. The winning team (Donald Trump's campaign team) engaged the services of Cambridge Analytica. Cambridge Analytica (CA) was a British political consulting firm that combines data mining, data brokerage and data analysis with strategic communication for election processes (Cambridge Analytica Politica, 2018).

Cambridge Analytica was contracted by the Trump campaign team, and they provided an entirely new weapon for the electoral battle. In addition to using

demographic segments to identify voters, just like the Clinton campaign did, Cambridge Analytica also performed psychographic segmentation. Demographics refers to information related to the class, education, occupation, age, etc., of a group or population. According to Suwarman, psychographics is an instrument used to measure lifestyle; it provides quantitative measurements and is used to analyse extensive data. Psychographic analysis is typically used to look at market segments; it is also interpreted as a consumer research that describes the consumer segment regarding their lives, jobs, and other activities (Suwarman, 2001:58).

In April 2018, a serious case about the unauthorised use of Facebook account data by Cambridge Analytica emerged. The data of as many as 50 million Facebook users from the United States was accessed and used by Cambridge Analytica. Christopher Wylie, former head of research at Cambridge Analytica who becoming the whistleblower in the case, designed the Psychological Operation (Psyop); this is an operating system to convey specific information, affect the user's emotions, motivate, and provide objective reasons. To explore voters, they collect many people's data to build their psychological profiles (kompas.com). Cambridge Analytica made efforts to construct and frame community thinking in determining its choice in the 2016 election in the United States.

At that time, there was an app called "This Is Your Digital Life" on Facebook, and this app could provide exclusive access not just to the personal data of the users of the app, but also the personal data of the network of friends of the app users. The app is able to retrieve the data of users, such as what they like, etc. The app was downloaded by 270,000 Facebook accounts across the United States, but its impact affected the data of about 50 to 60 million users (Kompas.com).

Indonesia, that will hold Presidential elections in 2019, does not have a specific policy and regulation on the protection of personal data. The provisions on this issue are still contained separately in several legislations and only reflect certain aspects of the security of personal data in general. Concerning the protection of private data in developing countries, Indonesia is vulnerable because it is yet to pass the Personal Data Protection (PDP) Act for its citizens. The provisions on this issue are not contained in a single legislation and only covers some aspects of the security of personal data. The regulations include the following: Law Number 7 Year 1971 regarding Principal Provisions of Filing, Law Number 8 Year 1997 concerning Company Document, Law Number 10 Year 1998 concerning Amendment to Law Number 7 Year 1992 concerning Banking, Law Number 36 Year 2009 on Health, Law Number 36 Year 1999 on Telecommunication, and Law Number 23 Year 2006 regarding Population Administration. It is relevant to note that fellow Southeast Asian nations, including the Philippines, Malaysia, and Singapore, have passed the PDP Law, while Brunei, Thailand, and Vietnam are discussing it in their respective parliaments. It is worthy of note that some countries in Africa whose digital infrastructure are not as good as that of Indonesia already have a PDP Act (Kompas.com).

The PDP Act serves to make people in a country feel comfortable in using social media, as it can safeguard their data in such a way that no one except the government may access them. The issue of theft of private data for business interests has occurred in Indonesia, but there has been no civil and criminal law action on the subject. So what if the case of using private data for politics and power interests, which happened in the United States, occurs in Indonesia? This issue is a very sensitive issue in the world today because personal data is basically secret data and only the owner of the account and the site manager should have access to it. This paper will discuss the issue of private data protection in Indonesia ahead of the 2019 Presidential Election. It will also discuss the impact of the dissemination of private Facebook data, which has created a new campaign concept. Countries where the Personal Data Protection (PDP) Act is not yet in force are more vulnerable.

Research Methodology

This research is a descriptive-analytical research. Data collection was done by literature research; library research was done to obtain secondary data, and a literature review of some online media references, such as online magazine sites from several countries.

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